

JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry
Faculty of Physical Sciences
University of Maiduguri
<https://jsrunimaid.com>

Research Article

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10676632>

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF EMULSION PAINT BINDER FROM COPOLYMER COMPOSITE OF TRIMETHYLOL UREA/HYDROXYLATED AFRICAN LOCUST BEAN (*Parkia biglobosa*) OIL

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ABSTRACT

*In this study, trimethylol urea from urea formaldehyde was modified with Hydroxylated African Locust Bean Seed Oil (HALBSO) (*Parkia biglobosa*) so as to satisfy some specific requirements for water-based binders. The copolymerization was carried out at different concentrations (10 - 60%). The results showed that the copolymer composite of trimethylol urea and hydroxylated african locust bean seed oil (TMU/HALBSO) is more water resistant, softer and more flexible and can compete favorably than some convectional paint binders. The blending at 50:50 has succeeded in reducing the emission level lower than the permissible level of 0.1 ppm. The different levels of interactions gave rise to polymers with different morphology and crosslink density. The density of the amino resin, decreases gradually with increase in HALBSO concentration and this trend is attributed to differences in the molecular features and morphology which influences the packing nature of resin molecules. TMU and HALBSO copolymer resin present itself as a good binder for the formulation emulsion paint.*

Keywords: Trimethylol Urea; Hydroxylated Locust Beans Seed Oil; Copolymerization; Binder; Emulsion Paint

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric products are unique materials that exhibit different durability based on the backbone of its chain. Those consisting of components with different properties are usually known to possess some advantages over the individual polymers [1]. As the use of polymers has increased in numerous applications, the issue of polymer waste disposal has also gained significant concern of the polymer system. Urea formaldehyde (UF) resin is a polymeric condensation product of the chemical reaction of formaldehyde with amine functional compounds such as melamine and urea, and is considered as one of the most important wood adhesives. They are extremely tough and show resistant to scratch, with major application in industrial purpose. Some advantages of urea formaldehyde resin include low price, good technological properties, absence of colors in cured polymer and easiness of application [2-3]. However, its acceptance as a universal material in the coating industry is limited by some of its inherent qualities such as brittleness, poor water resistance and formaldehyde emission. Therefore, for application in coatings and for the manufacturing of different valuable products, urea formaldehyde could be modified to satisfy some specific requirements for water-based coats.

Vegetable oils on the hand are triglycerides in which C_{18} carboxylic acids are dominant. Some of the fatty acids derived from these triglycerides are unsaturated [4]. Vegetable oils are an important component for both food (for feeding, margarine and canned food industry, bakery, confectionery) and for non-food industry (production of detergents, paints, special varnishes, fatty acids, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics products). Vegetable oils, due to their abundant availability, low cost, renewability, biodegradability and environmentally friendly nature have growing interest in utilizing the vegetable oil as precursor in chemical applications [5]. These attributes possessed by various vegetable oil made them successful materials for replacement of petroleum-based resources [6].

African locust bean oil is a vegetable oil obtained from the seed of African locust bean tree. Due to its hydrophobic nature and the presence of functional groups that could be involved in chemical reactions, they can be perfectly incorporated to obtain a mid-product of desirable products. Their use as blending tools offers numerous advantages such as low toxicity, gloss and inherent biodegradability [7]. Chemical modification of vegetable oils can effectively improve their uses as precursor in production of important materials such as resin, lubricants, surfactants, plasticizers, biodiesel, polyol etc. [6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Urea, formaldehyde, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, sulphuric acid, sodium hydroxide, sucrose, distilled water, hydrogen peroxide, acetic acid, formic acid, iso-propanol, methanol, n-hexane (all of analytical grades), and locust bean seed oil (LBSO). Soxhlet extractor, condenser, round bottom flask, heating mantle, weighing balance and rotary evaporator were some of the apparatus used.

Resin Synthesis

The one step process (OSP) as reported by Osemeahon and Archibong [8] was adopted. One mole of urea (6.0 g) was made to react with three moles of formaldehyde (24.3 mL) 37% (w/v) (methylation reaction), using 0.2 g of sodium dihydrogen phosphate as catalyst. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6 by using 0.5 M H_2SO_4 and 1.0 M NaOH solutions. The solution was heated in a thermostatically controlled water bath at 70°C. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 hr after which the resin was removed and kept at room temperature (30°C).

Epoxidation of African Locust Bean (*Parkia biglobosa*) Oil (ALBO)

Epoxidation was carried out using the method described by Goud *et al.* [9]. 200 mL of the African locust bean oil was introduced in a 500 mL three necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser and a thermocouple. The flask was placed on a hot plate with temperature control. Acetic acid and formic acid at a molar ratio of 0.5:1 to the oil and sulphuric acid catalyst 3% weight of hydrogen peroxide as an oxygen carrier was added into the African locust bean seed oil. A hydrogen peroxide of molar ratio 1.5:1 to the African locust bean seed oil was added drop wise into the mixture. This feeding strategy is required in order to avoid overheating the system since epoxidation is an exothermic reaction. The uniformity of the reaction was maintained by using a magnetic stirrer which runs at 1600 rpm under isothermal condition at 50 – 60°C. The product was cooled and decanted in order to separate the organic-soluble compounds (epoxidized locust bean seed oil) from water-soluble compounds. Warm water was used to wash the epoxidized oil (in small aliquots) in order to remove residual contaminants. This procedure was repeated in triplicates.

Hydroxylation of Epoxidised African Locust Bean Oil

Hydroxylation of the epoxidized African locust bean oil was carried out using procedure described by Petrovic *et al.* [10]. The reaction was performed in a 1000 mL three necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser and a thermocouple. The flask was placed on a hot plate with temperature control. 150 mL of the epoxidized African locust bean oil was hydroxylated using alcohol (methanol and isopropanol) with a molar ratio of 4:1 to the oil and water at a molar ratio of 2:1 was mixed with the epoxidized African locust bean oil and sulphuric acid catalyst in the reactor. The reaction was performed at a fixed temperature of 60°C for 5 hr. Uniformity was maintained by using a magnetic stirrer which runs at 1600 rpm. The product (polyol) was cooled and decanted in order to separate the organic-soluble compounds from water-soluble compounds. Warm water was used to wash the polyol (in small aliquots) in order to remove residual contaminants. This procedure was repeated in triplicates.

Copolymerization

This was carried out by blending different concentrations (10 – 60%) of epoxidized African locust bean oil in TMU. The mixture was stirred with glass rod and left for 24 hr at room temperature (30°C).

Determination of some Physicochemical Properties of Resins

The solubility of the resins in water, elongation at break and the moisture uptake were determined by the method described by [8, 11]. Formaldehyde test was performed by using the standard 2 hr desiccator method [12]; the procedure by [8] was adopted for the viscosity measurements. The gel point of the resin was determined by measuring the viscosity of the resin with time until a constant viscosity profile was obtained. The density, turbidity, melting points and refractive index were determined according to standard method [13].

Paint Formulation

The method described by [14] was adopted for the paint formulation. The method splits the production process into three main stages as illustrated in Table 1, while the mixture in each stage was stirred for 15 min using a mechanical stirrer.

Table 1: Recipe for the Formulation of Emulsion Paints from TMU/HALBSO Binders.

Stage	Material	Quantity (g)
First	Water	185
	Antifoam	0.2
	Drier	0.2
	Calgon	1.16
	Genepour	1.16
	Bermocoll	2.50
	Troystan	1.14
	Dispersant	0.2
	Butanol	5.0
	Ammonia	0.54
Second (Millbase)	TiO ₂	50.00
	Al ₂ SiO ₃	11.20
	Na ₂ CO ₃	0.58
	Kaolin [Al ₂ Si ₂ O ₅ (OH) ₄]	2.52
	CaCO ₃	123.00
Third (Letdown)	Binder	100.00
	Water	15.00
	Dispersant	0.2
	Nicofoam	0.2
	Anti-skinning Agent	0.2
Total		500

Test Procedures for Paint Samples

The analyses of the paint samples were done as described by standard organization of Nigeria methods [13; 15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Physicochemical properties of TMU, TMU/HALBSO and the comparison with accepted levels in the coating industry

	TMU	TMU/HALBSO	Accepted Level in the coating Industry [8]
Density (gcm ⁻³)	1.117	1.073	1.07 (Min.)
Refractive Index	1.405	1.417	1.4000 (Min.)
Formaldehyde Emission (ppm)	0.0912	0.0435	0.1 (Max.)
Moisture Uptake (%)	4.750	1.160	3.10 (Max.)
Gel time (hrs)	209	56	-
Solubility	Soluble	Sparingly soluble	-
Turbidity (NTU)	121	632	-
Viscosity (mpa.s)	3.00	18.99	3.11 – 38.00
Melting point (C°)	263.2	202.10	200 (maximum)
Appearance	Transparence	Off-white	-
Elongation at break	27	122	125 (minimum)

The physicochemical properties of the TMU and TMU/HALBSO are presented in Table 2. The Table also inter-compares the values with the accepted level in the coating industry. The results explained that the TMU/HALBSO is more water resistant, softer and more flexible and can compete favorably than some convectional paint binders. This result also suggests that the problems of poor water resistance, hardness and brittleness associated with convectional urea formaldehyde [1] is been addressed through blending of TMU with HALBSO. However, the gloss of HALBSO modified resin is relatively higher compared to the literature value; this can be attributed to the orientation and a state of aggregation established by ALBSO, thereby creating light scattering boundaries and discontinuities in the molecular structure of the copolymer composite [3].

Formaldehyde Emission

The effect of HALBSO concentration on the formaldehyde emission of TMU/HALBSO resin is represented on figure 1. It is observed that the emission level decreased with increase in the percentage of HALBSO inclusion in the blend. This trend is due to the gradual decrease in the trimethylol urea content with increase in the HALBSO content in the blend [16]. The blending process has succeeded in reducing the emission level lower than the permissible level of 0.1 ppm

Fig. 1: Effect of HALBSO concentration on the formaldehyde emission of TMU/HALBSO

Moisture Uptake

Figure 2 shows the effect of HALBSO on the moisture uptake of trimethylol urea resin. It can be seen that the moisture uptake decreased slightly at the beginning and steeply above 10% blend. The different levels of interactions gave rise to polymers with different morphology and crosslink density [17]. Above 0 - 10% the molecular sizes of holesin HALBSO inclusion resulting to a step reduction in moisture uptake.

Fig. 2: Effect of HALBSO concentration on the moisture uptake of TMU/HALBSO resin

Density

The effect of HALBSO concentration on the density of TMU/HALBSO resin is represented in figure 3. It shows the effect of HALBSO on the density of trimethylol urea where the density of the amino resin, decreases gradually with increase in HALBSO concentration. This trend may be due to differences in the molecular features and morphology which influences the packing nature of resin molecules [18].

Density of TMU/HALBSO Resin

Fig. 3: Effect of HALBSO concentration on the density of TMU/HALBSO resin

CONCLUSION

Copolymerization of TMU and HALBSO resins was successfully carried out in this study. Some physical properties such as gel time, viscosity, density, melting point, moisture uptake, refractive index and formaldehyde emission level were evaluated. The blending showed that chemical interaction occurs between TMU and HALBSO. Resin from the copolymer possess superior optical property, density, water resistance, flexibility, softness and lower formaldehyde emission than the conventional resin. Some physical properties of the copolymer showed agreement with the literature values of other types of binders used in paints formulations. The flexibility, adhesion, hardness and resistance to blistering, viscosity and drying time of the formulated emulsion paint using TMU/HALBSO falls within the accepted range of SON in the coating industry. In conclusion

therefore, the copolymer composite of TMU/HALBSO present itself as a potential binder for water – based paint formulation.

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